

Deleted:

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: YOHOU****FIRST NAME: KEVIN SYLVESTRE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA_401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Deleted:

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List of key concepts with the page number in the text:

1. Preparatory stage of drafting (EUCLID 2021, 7-9)
2. Structure of a research article (EUCLID 2021,10-12)
3. Submission process (EUCLID 2021, 13-14)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 14)

Commented [GK1]: At least 5 concepts are required!

Deleted:

WRITING A CLASSIC RESEARCH ARTICLE

1) INTRODUCTION

Science is the orderly collection of observations about the natural world made via well-defined procedures, and modern science is an archive of scientific papers, told Michael Jay Katz.

Deleted: «

Deleted: »

As part of my courses for the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Global Health and Health Systems, I initiated research on the development of a research article. Indeed, scientific research requires the production of quality scientific articles.

Commented [GK2]: In UK English, personal and degree titles are not punctuated!

The scientific article is an element of dissemination of a scientific study to share the main results obtained. Throughout this article, we will first present the preparatory stages of a scientific article, then we will discuss the different parts of the writing and the process of elaboration and submission of the scientific article.

Based on my experience and the scientific literature review, I propose some elements of scientific article writing to help in the writing of a classic research article.

Deleted:

2) PREPARATORY STAGES OF DRAFTING

The preparation of scientific papers is very important and must be done in a rigorous way to report a scientific study. "Early start-up: It is best to start as early as possible. One of the initial things required for writing is to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write." (Cleenerwerck and Gulma 2021, 7)

a) Identification of the topic

The subject must have certain characteristics that make it attractive. Indeed, the topic must be relevant, topical, original and of interest to science.

b) Literature review

Once the research topic has been identified, a review of the scientific literature must be carried out. The literature review can help to refine the research theme or topic.

3) STRUCTURE OF A RESEARCH ARTICLE

Generally speaking, in the presentation of an article, "a title, a list of authors with their institutional affiliations (generally academic) and an abstract open the article and a list of ordered bibliographic references close it" (Flandrin 2012, 1).

The writing of a scientific article obeys the rules of scientific journals in which, among other things, the different constituent parts of the structure of the scientific article are summarized under the acronym "IMRaD", namely: Introduction; Material and Method; Results; Discussion; and Conclusion.

The general rules of the structure of the classical research article are thus described in detail, but it is important to follow the instructions of the authors of the scientific journals in which the article will be published.

a) Introduction

The introduction should be short and should situate the reader on the context and interest of the study. Furthermore, this section should specify the aims and objectives of the study, and "the structure should funnel down from a broad perspective to a specific aim of the study". (Todorovic 2003, 203)

Commented [GK3]: Note that periods are only placed AFTER citations and not before them even if direct quotes are involved!

Commented [GK4]: Since you cited the course pack as (EUCLID 2021, 7) in the list of key concepts, continue with that style. Or if you refer to use names, change the citations in the list of key concepts. In anyway, try to be uniform.

Deleted: m

Deleted: c

b) Material and method

This section of the paper should describe in detail and comprehensively how the study was designed and implemented, the period of the study, the setting of the study, the human, material, and financial resources needed to implement the study, and the materials and methods used. The main objective is to describe in detail the study protocol to allow its replicability by other researchers. "This is critically important as the obtained results should be reproducible if they are to be of scientific merit". (Todorovic 2003, 203)

This section will specify how the data will be collected, captured, and analyzed by ethical conditions.

"The study design should be stated up front because each study type has its strengths and limitations, and usually dictates the type of statistical tests that are appropriate for analyzing the data and describing the results". (Todorovic 2003, 203)

c) Results

This section will present the main results of the objectives of the study. The sharing of observations on these results will be done to appreciate the trends. "It is easy to see that it consists not only of text but also of formulas, tables, graphs (and even today of links to multimedia documents such as visual or/and sound animations)". (Flandrin 2012, 2)

d) Discussion

This section deals with the interpretation of the main results, the implications of these results, and the open questions raised by these results. The results were compared with those of similar studies carried out by other authors listed in the literature review. This section may highlight the added value of the study in the evolution of research in a specific field.

e) Conclusion

At the end of the scientific article, it is advisable to include a conclusion section which should succinctly present the main findings of the study and outline the perspectives arising from them. It is not necessary to repeat all the results and other sections of the research article.

4) SUBMISSION PROCESS

a) Constitution of the writing team

The drafting of a scientific article can be individual but in the majority of cases, it is collegial work. The writing team of a scientific article is composed of researchers or people with different profiles who may or may not have participated in the scientific study from which the scientific article is derived. Each of the editors contributes to the development of the article according to his or her field of specialization.

b) Plagiarism

Ethical research requires respect for copyright and, to this end, the need to refrain from arrogating to oneself results, quotations, and conclusions that do not originate from the study that is presented in the scientific article.

"Authors must learn to master the codes for citations (inverted commas, indents, typography, etc.), and this in all disciplines. Citations must be placed in a very identifiable place in the text".(Leduc et al. 2017, 18)

c) Dissemination or submission of the article to a scientific journal

The visibility of the researcher and the sharing of new knowledge are the main reasons that lead to the dissemination of research products. (Wee and Banister 2016, 9)

Before writing any journal paper it is important to think about the journal of the first choice for submission.

Once your draft is complete, it's time to edit. Continuity, in both substance and style, should be at the forefront of your mind during this process, and the initial blueprint will help ensure that the experiments and conclusions flow continuously in a logical succession. Your writing style is just that - yours - but keep your writing clear and concise by avoiding very long sentences, as well as fragmented ones. (Gemayel 2016, 3883)

Once the authors have developed and validated the research article, it should be submitted to a peer-reviewed scientific journal. Preference should be given to a specialist scientific journal that considers the research topic's theme. The submission process can be iterative and leads to the publication of the article in the scientific journal once the authors have taken into account the comments of the readers.

Submitting a scientific article to a scientific journal is a process that starts with the writing of the article and must follow the general rules of the targeted scientific journal.

Deleted:

5) CONCLUSION

Writing a research article is an important step in reporting a research study. I have tried to share some tips to help writers improve the quality of the content of scientific articles. From the preparatory stages to the submission and drafting of scientific articles, it is important to respect the rules set out to better share the knowledge acquired.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Deleted: "

Flandrin, Patrick. 2012. "Écritures : Écrire un article." *Presses de l'enssib*, 214–27. <https://doi.org/10.4000/books.pressesensib.1961>.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Gemayel, Rita. 2016. "How to Write a Scientific Paper." *The FEBS Journal* 283, no. 21 (November): 3882–85. <https://doi.org/10.1111/febs.13918>.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Leduc, Michèle, Lucienne Letellier, Antoinette Molinié, Nathalie Nevejans, Jean-Gabriel Ganascia, and Rémy Mosseri. 2017. "COMETS AVIS 2017-34 : Réflexion éthique sur le plagiat dans la recherche scientifique." 20. (hal-02138971) <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02138971>

Todorovic, Ljubomir. 2003. "original (scientific) paper : The IMRAD Layout." *Archive of Oncology* 11, no. 3 : 203 – 5.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Wee, Bert Van, and David Banister. 2016. "How to Write a Literature Review Paper ?" *Transport Reviews* 36, no. 2 (March): 278–88. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2015.1065456>.

Formatted: Font: Italic

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.